

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Deliverable 3.1

Online Submission and Evaluation System and Templates for the Proposal Submission

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1 Introduction

The overall aim of WP3 is to manage internal calls of the EJP SOIL open to EJP SOIL partners and linked third parties according to the consortium agreement to fill research and development gaps identified by WPs 2, 5, 6 & 8 by means of on-demand stocktake activities and competitive internal calls. Finalized internal calls will be opened and incoming proposals will be evaluated based on their i) excellence, ii) impact, and iii) quality and efficiency of the implementation. In detail the project management process provided by WP3 is articulated in four sub-objectives: i) Preparation of call texts and call documents, ii) launching calls and managing entire evaluation process, iii) monitoring progress and managing reporting of each EJP SOIL funded project to ensure timely production of agreed deliverables and to verify projects progress during annual and progress reporting; and iv) coordinating synchronization of all outputs of the EJP SOIL funded projects. Setting up standard operating procedures (SOPs) provides standardized approaches of regularly recurring operations that are relevant to assure quality.

The procedures presented in each SOP have been developed by WP3 based on existing knowledge and approaches used at LUKE (Finland), INIA-CSIC (i.e. former INIA; Spain) and the PtJ Juelich GmbH (Germany). The first set of SOPs are general i) justifying and explaining how to use the SOPs during executing WP3 tasks and activities and providing names and contact details of involved experts. Another set of SOPs relates to task-specific activities addressing i) call preparation, ii) Submission and call office, iii) Proposal evaluation, and iv) Project monitoring. The SOPs present a generic approach covering all task-specific activities, but are adjustable in case of changing circumstances. Thus, it is expected that this document will be updated overtime.

2 General SOPs

2.1 SOP-GW 01 Working with SOP

“A Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) is a document which describes the regularly recurring operations relevant to the quality of the investigation. The purpose of a SOP is to carry out the operations correctly and always in the same manner. A SOP should be available at the place where the work is done” (FAO)¹.

1. Objective

This SOP describes the function of and procedures around the SOP’s for the **Management of Internal Calls (Work Package 3) within the European Joint Programme on Soils (EJP SOIL; Project No. 862695)** coordinated by LUKE. These SOP’s are written to standardize the way the LUKE and linked staff from BIOS (Austria) and INIA-CSIC (in 2021 INIA merged with CSIC, Spain) prepare, launch and manage the EJP SOIL Internal Calls, and should be seen as a compulsory instruction.

2. Procedure description

2.1 SOP structure

- 2.1.1 SOP’s are subdivided in two categories: general SOP (SOP-G) and operational SOP (SOP-O). Category of the SOP is followed by its number and version. SOP-Gs explain purpose of SOPs, roles and duties of involved staff from LUKE, BIOS/BOKU, and INIA-CSIC. SOP-Os describe procedures to organize, handle, and monitor EJP SOIL Internal calls.
- 2.1.2 The digital copy of each SOP is named as followed: “SOP category”-“SOP number”-“SOP version”-“SOP title” (e.g. “SOP-GW 01 – Working with SOPs”).

2.2 SOP responsibilities

The LUKE is responsible for the content and timely updating of the SOP’s. The current version is described in **SOP-GW 01** and stored as DOC and PDF files at LUKE’s administrative SharePoint ([EJP_SOIL_H2020_41007-00185500](https://ejp-soil.h2020.41007-00185500)) and in copy as PDF file at the [EJP SOIL’s SharePoint](#) managed by INRAE.

2.3 SOP content

- 2.3.1 All SOP pages contain the title, SOP number, version, issue date, expiry date, page number, total pages and total amount of digital copies (including the original).
- 2.3.2 The SOP describes purpose, procedure, required equipment, materials, chemicals, safety issues, required training and related documents.

¹ <http://www.fao.org/3/W7295E/w7295e04.htm>; accessed on 16th May 2020

- 2.3.3 On the last page of each SOP the author and responsible person sign (digital signatures are accepted) the original document.
- 2.3.4 In this set of SOP's staff refers to all personnel, whether they are staff, students, guests or other have a different designation.

2.4 Working with SOP's

- 2.4.1 The descriptions in the SOP documents are mandatory.
- 2.4.2 Consult the LUKE (i.e. Nils Borchard and Johanna Leppälä) when deviations from the SOP are required.
- 2.4.3 All LUKE staff working in WP3 and all members of EJP SOIL should have access to the current SOP's, but NOT to call texts under preparation (see also respective **SOP-OC 01 "Call preparation"**).

2.5 SOP updating and storage

- 2.5.1 The LUKE is responsible for timely SOP updating (i.e. per Internal Call). This needs to be done before the expiry date and/or when there is a procedural change. The SOP should at all times reflect current best practices. During the update the version number will be changes (one up). The new document is signed and copies are distributed to the correct locations.
- 2.5.2 Soft copies of the previous version will be removed but the original is transferred to the digital SOP archive (at LUKE's administrative SharePoint ([EJP_SOIL_H2020_41007-00185500](https://sharepoint.luke.fi/EJP_SOIL_H2020_41007-00185500))).
- 2.5.3 LUKE's Tiimeri is open for LUKE staff members and external experts after creating an account as follows (LUKE's ICT office: Ganeas Dorairaju, ganeas.dorairaju@luke.fi): i) submit e-mail address (rather a private one) to WP3 leader (Nils Borchard, nils.borchard@luke.fi or WP3 manager Johanna Leppälä, johanna.leppala@luke.fi) who will grant access by responding with an e-mail invitation with a link to Tiimeri folder, ii) following the link and logging in via e-mail finalizes registration; use "valtioneuvoston palvelu" and "LUKE".

2.6 Copies

- 2.6.1. There are two versions of each SOP (unless otherwise specified), one original at LUKE's Tiimeri share-point for administration ([EJP_SOIL_H2020_41007-00185500](https://sharepoint.luke.fi/EJP_SOIL_H2020_41007-00185500)) and one soft copy at the [EJP SOIL's SharePoint](https://sharepoint.luke.fi/EJP_SOIL_H2020_41007-00185500) managed by INRAE. It is not allowed to remove, edit, and copy from LUKE's Tiimeri share-point and to remove from EJP SOIL's SharePoint.

2.7 Creating new SOP's

New procedures require their own SOP. Numbering of the new SOP will be in ascending order. A new SOP cannot receive a number which already belongs to another SOP, not even a number from a deleted.

2.8 Deleting existing SOP's

When a SOP is made redundant the digital copies will be removed but the original will be transferred to the digital archive without replacing it with a new version. The remaining SOP's will keep their original numbering.

WP3 manager

Name: Johanna Leppälä

Date: 9th July 2021

Signature: _____

WP3 leader

Name: Nils Borchard

Date: 9th July 2021

Signature: _____

2.2 SOP-GR 01 Roles and responsibilities

1. Objective

This SOP describes the roles and responsibilities of persons that are directly and indirectly involved in preparing, launching, and managing Internal Calls of the European Joint Programme on Soils (EJP SOIL; Project No. 862695) coordinated by LUKE.

2. Direct involvements

2.1 Responsibilities at LUKE

Programme Manager: Johanna Buchert (johanna.buchert@luke.fi); +358 29 5326 663; The Programme Manager has been mandated by the Finish Program Owner (i.e. the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry) to manage the programme on their behalf.

WP3 leader: Nils Borchard (nils.borchard@luke.fi); +358 29 5322 201; The WP leader ensures that proposed goals will be achieved. The WP leader will assign tasks to participants/team members and set goals for individuals and for milestones.

WP3 manager: Johanna Leppälä (johanna.leppala@luke.fi); +358 29 5322 559; The WP3 project manager focuses on deadlines, accomplishments, and budget, she is responsible for most day-to-day tasks, operational tasks, and responsible for communicating with team members.

Administrative officer: Sinikka Västilä (sinikka.vastila@luke.fi); +358 29 5322 152; The administrative officer is responsible to provide administrative support to LUKE's EJP SOIL team. Some duties include organizing LUKE records, reminding and scheduling budget and office reporting and invoicing.

Financial officer: Timo-Pekka Äikäs (timo.aikas@luke.fi); +358 29 5322 202; The financial officer has primary responsibility for managing LUKE's finances, including financial planning, management of risks, record-keeping, financial reporting, and supporting LUKE's WP3 team.

Communication officer: Elina Nurmi (elina.nurmi@luke.fi); +358 29 5322 092; Elina will act as LUKE's communication officer who will write, disseminate, and distribute EJP SOIL and WP3 related content in collaboration with WPs 8 and 9.

ICT officer: Ganeas Dorairaju (ganeas.dorairaju@luke.fi); +358 29 5322 134; The ICT officer will implement WP3-related ICT services (see also **SOP-OS 01 "Submission tool and call office"**), be responsible for documentation (see also **SOP-OS 01 "Submission tool and call office"**), and ensure use of up-to date services and technologies.

Legal officers: Hanna Lindqvist (hanna.lindqvist@luke.fi); +358 29 5322 338; The legal officers is responsible for monitoring all EJP SOIL and WP3 related legal affairs. She oversees in collaboration with LUKE lawyers both internal and external legal concerns aiming to keep LUKE out of legal trouble.

2.2 Finnish Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry

Programme owner: Marjaana Suorsa (marjaana.suorsa@mmm.fi); The Programme Owner is responsible for defining, financing or managing programme carried out at national or regional level.

Deputy programme owner: Not nominated.

2.3 BIOS/BOKU

WP3 deputy leader: Rosemarie Stangl (rosemarie.stangl@boku.ac.at); +43 1 47654 87401 and Pia Minixhofer (pia.minixhofer@boku.ac.at); +43 1 47654 87406; The BIOS/BOKU team assures quality of drafted texts and procedures via internal reviews and revisions. It co-manages the call office.

2.4 INIA-CSIC

WP3 partner: Elena Rodriguez (rodriguez.elena@inia.es) +34 91 347 6890 and Violeta Carrasco (violeta.carrasco@inia.es); The INIA team will ensure proper monitoring and evaluation of EJP SOIL projects launched within WP3.

3. Indirect involvements

3.1 Responsibilities at the PtJ Juelich

Ulrike Ziegler (u.ziegler@fz-juelich.de; +49 2429 908 95 77); Collaboration to ensure alignment of procedures used in WPs 3 and 4.

3.2 Responsibilities at the Teagasc

Raymond Kelly (Raymond.Kelly@teagasc.ie; +353 59 9183505); Collaboration in setting up and managing pool of external evaluators to be invited to evaluate proposals prepared to apply for Internal (WP3) and External (WP4) EJP SOIL funding.

WP3 manager

Name: Johanna Leppälä

Date: 9th July 2021

Signature: _____

WP3 leader

Name: Nils Borchard

Date: 9th July 2021

Signature: _____

3 Specific SOPs

3.1 SOP-OC 01 Call preparation

1. Objective

This SOP describes the standard procedures required to prepare, launch, and manage Internal Calls of the European Joint Programme Soils (EJP SOIL; Project No. 862695), which are coordinated by LUKE.

2. Implementing EJP SOIL's Internal calls

The EJP SOIL's procedures are adapted on procedures and recommendations described and given on the ERA-LEARN Platform (i.e. [Support for P2Ps](#)). Thus, implementation of EJP SOIL's Internal Calls includes following steps:

- 1) [Call planning and preparation](#); this SOP (**SOP-OC 01**) and D3.2 "Call text of the EJP SOIL 1st internal call"
 - 2) [Submission](#); see **SOP-OS 01**
 - 3) [Evaluation](#); see **SOP-OE 01** and D3.2 "Call text of the EJP SOIL 1st internal call"
 - 4) [Funding decision](#); this SOP (**SOP OC 01**)
 - 5) [After call tasks](#) (e.g. monitoring; see also **SOP-OM 01**)
- Call planning and preparation
 - Pre-announcements and final call announcements are based on outputs produced in T2.6. T2.6 output provides information on stocktaking activities and projects and their scopes, objectives, and deliverables.
 - Call announcements (Call announcement templates [pre-announcement/call announcement]; **SOP-OC 01 Annex 1a/b**) will include also deadlines, eligibility and selection criteria and procedures, and how to confirm financial commitment (Letter of Commitment; **SOP-OC 01 Annex 2.docx**), reporting obligations (Reporting template; **SOP-OC 01 Annex 3.docx**), dissemination activities, and instructions for submissions of proposals.
 - LUKE will gather and prepare evaluation results prior forwarding to the Board of Project Managers (BPM). Thus, LUKE's role (role of WP3) does not include evaluation and project selection, which will be based on external evaluations and decision made at the BPM.
 - Pre-announcements and call announcements will be published on the EJP SOIL's webpage (WP9), which the EJP SOIL will publish and disseminate internally *via* internal newsletters.
 - The outcome of the selection procedure will be communicated by the Call Office to the project coordinators, who are responsible to inform beneficiaries about the result.

WP3 manager
Name: Johanna Leppälä
Date: 9th July 2021
Signature: _____

WP3 leader
Name: Nils Borchard
Date: 9th July 2021
Signature: _____

3.2 SOP-OS 01 Submission tool and call office

1. Objective

This SOP describes procedures prepared to set up and operate the EJP SOIL's online submission system and call office required to manage Internal Calls.

2. Submission approach

- Online submission system consisting of a data secure collaborative service SharePoint environment (operated by Valtori Oy – Finnish Government ICT Centre) and an online submission system based on a Finnish system (www.lyyti.com) and operated by LUKE (Johanna Leppälä and ICT expert Krista Kettunen [krista.kettunen@luke.fi]) will be set up in advance of each call announcement.
- Access to call-specific SharePoints and online submission systems limited in two persons (i.e. Nils Borchard [nils.borchard@luke.fi] and Johanna Leppälä [johanna.leppala@luke.fi]).
- Submission instructions will be published on the EJP SOIL's webpage and distributed via the EJP SOIL National Communication Representative (WP9).

3. Call office

- Call office is aimed to provide services to coordinators and evaluators during proposal preparation, evaluation and lifetime of funded projects (see for more details Call announcement template; **SOP-OC 01 Annex 1.docx**).
- Deputy regulations will ensure proper operation of the EJP SOIL's call office supporting Internal Calls.

WP3 Manager

Name: Johanna Leppälä

Date: 9th July 2021

Signature: _____

WP3 leader

Name: Nils Borchard

Date: 9th July 2021

Signature: _____

3.3 SOP-OE 01 Proposal evaluation

1. Objective

This SOP describes procedures set up to manage evaluation and selection of submitted proposals prepared to apply for EJP SOIL internal funding.

2. Evaluation approach

- Submitted proposal will be evaluated by WP3 for their eligibility based on eligibility criteria stated on the call announcement. Eligible proposals will be forwarded to invited evaluators (see Letter of Request to the EC, [SOP-OE 01 Annex 1.docx](#), Non-Disclosure Agreement, [SOP-OE 01 Annex 2.docx](#))
 - Pool of external experts will be managed in collaboration with WP4 (Teagasc).
 - The EJP SOIL's pool of external experts is built up based on the European Commission database of experts and those searched on the internet (e.g. authors of articles listed in Web of Knowledge, and experts in research institutions and organisations). Access has been granted to Nils Borchard (nils.borchard@luke.fi), and Pia Minixhofer (pia.minixhofer@boku.ac.at).
 - Selection of evaluators includes a check for potential conflicts of interests. Reviewers have to sign confidentiality and declaration of conflict of interest statements (Non-Disclosure Agreement, [SOP-OE 01 Annex 2.docx](#)).
 - Reviewers will evaluate proposals in accordance to [ERA-LEARN evaluation guidelines](#) (see D3.2 "Call text of the EJP SOIL 1st internal call"; Evaluation guideline, [SOP-OE 01 Annex 3.docx](#); Evaluation report, [SOP-OE 01 Annex 4.docx](#)).
- a. Proposal will be ranked based on reported excellence, impact, quality and efficiency of the implementation. List(s) of ranked projects will be forwarded to the Board of Project Managers for final decision making prior informing coordinators. Final list of project approved by the Board of Program Managers will be delivered to the European Commission (see deliverables of WP3 in the Grant Agreement and SOP-OE 01 Annex 5).

WP3 manager

Name: Johanna Leppälä

Date: 9th July 2021

Signature: _____

WP3 leader

Name: Nils Borchard

Date: 9th July 2021

Signature: _____

3.4 SOP-OM 01 Project monitoring and evaluation

1. Objective

This SOP deals with the standard procedures to monitor, report, evaluate and closing research projects. **Monitoring** is the collection and analysis of information about a project, undertaken while the project is ongoing. **Evaluation** is the periodic, retrospective assessment of a project that might be conducted internally or by external independent evaluators.

2. Setting up a monitoring and evaluation system

In order to monitor and evaluate activities of internally funded EJP SOIL project a set of procedures needs to be set up:

- i) How to collect information? See questionnaires Annexes A and B of Reporting template in [SOP-OC-01 Annex 3.docx](#).
- ii) Define SMART indicators appropriate to monitor and evaluate performance; based on [SOP-OM-01 Annex 1.xlsx](#).
- iii) Monitoring and evaluation system of WP3 is aligned to the EJP SOIL monitoring and evaluation system managed by WP1.

3. Managing monitoring and evaluation of EJP SOIL-funded project

- i) Project coordinators are obliged to submit reports of continuous reporting (3 times a year) and end-term reports (i.e. ETR) using data secure and project-specific EJP SOIL SharePoint; see also Section 7 “Obligations for funded projects” in [SOP-OC-01 Annex 1b.docx](#).
- ii) For reports templates will be provided; see Annexes A and B of Reporting template in [SOP-OC-01 Annex 3.docx](#).
- iii) Evaluation of the reports will be conducted by WP3 in coordination with WP1 and the Board of Program Managers for Summary Progress reports approval.
- iv) After approving ETRs EJP SOIL-funded projects will be closed and catalogued with access of all EJP SOIL participants and donor.

WP3 manager

Name: Johanna Leppälä

Date: 9th July 2021

Signature: _____

WP3 leader

Name: Nils Borchard

Date: 9th July 2021

Signature: _____

Annexes

SOP-OC 01 Annex 1a (Pre-announcement)

Templates based on 1st EJP SOIL Call prepared and launched in 2020.

Timeline

The Internal Call will follow a **1-stage-procedure**. There will be a competitive selection. A time schedule is provided below:

Action	Schedule
Pre-Announcement	DD month YYYY
Launch of the Call	DD month YYYY
Webinar for interested applicants	DD month YYYY
Closing date for submission	DD month YYYY
Evaluation and Selection	DD month YYYY
Notification letters sent to coordinator	DD month YYYY
Contract negotiations between partners	DD month YYYY
Start of projects	DD month YYYY
End of projects	Depends on project size

Partnering tool

For partnering the EJP SOIL WP3 team launched **Slack Channels** (i.e. topic-specific chat rooms at www.slack.com). Access will be granted after sending an e-mail to the Call Office; see below. Access will be granted after sending an e-mail to the Call Office (EJPCO@maapera.fi). After access has been granted, applicants express their interest to participate and/or coordinate in one or even more topic-specific Slack Channels (i.e. a type of chat room). For each topic listed in Table 1 and Annex 2 the partnering tool offers a “chat room” (i.e. i.e. “cm2”, “cm8”, “mt1”, “sr5”, “es7”, “fs2-mt4”, “es1-es2”, “ca1”) and an embedded XLS file used to summarize the information. Applicants should add following information into the topic-specific chat rooms: Who am I? Where do I work? What is my expertise? What is my interest => participation/coordination? Finally, applicants should add their name and interest to participate and/or coordinate into the XLS file.

Call Office contacts

NAME:	Nils Borchard	Johanna Leppälä
Organisation:	LUKE	LUKE
Phone:	+358 29 5322 201	+358 29 5322 559
E-mail:	EJPCO@maapera.fi	EJPCO@maapera.fi
NAME:	Rosemarie Stangl	Pia Minixhofer
Organisation:	BIOS/BOKU	BIOS/BOKU
Phone:	+43 1 47854 87401	+43 1 47854 87406
E-mail:	EJPCO@maapera.fi	EJPCO@maapera.fi

1 Background of the Call

1.1 About the EJP SOIL

The EJP SOIL will maximize the contribution of agricultural soil towards achieving sustainability at multiple levels: **i) At the societal level:** raise public awareness and foster understanding of sustainable agricultural soil management and its contribution to food production, climate change adaptation and mitigation; **ii) At the scientific level:** develop new insights on climate-smart soil management, quantify trade-offs and synergies between agricultural production, climate change adaptation and mitigation, soil fertility and health and other ecosystem services; gather new knowledge on carbon sequestration in soils under different conditions across Europe and its contribution to climate change mitigation; improve accounting and reporting tools for emission and removals from agricultural activities; **iii) At the operational level:** strengthen the European research community on agricultural soil management; develop harmonized soil information systems and promote their adoption; **iv) At the policy level:** develop evidence-based recommendations for policy makers at EU, national, and regional levels; establish a strategic multi-actor approach and initiate a science-policy-practitioner-society dialogue on agricultural soil health and adequate agricultural practices to support the adoption of the policy recommendations; foster the uptake of climate-smart sustainable soil management practices by practitioners.

1.2. Rationale of this call

As EJP SOIL works on important societal issues in an integrated manner, any innovation developed within the framework of EJP SOIL will meet a societal need and will therefore be relevant for European and global markets. Through its knowledge framework, EJP SOIL improves its innovation capacity using 1) **knowledge development**, 2) knowledge sharing & transfer, 3) knowledge organization and storage for 4) knowledge application in different areas. **Knowledge development** will be supported by the EJP SOIL through a large number of specific research and innovation projects via internal (i.e. WP3 “Internal Calls”) and external EJP SOIL calls. The **overall objective of this internal call** is to fund stocktaking activities, synthesizes and research projects open to EJP SOIL beneficiaries and linked third parties (LTP) according to the consortium agreement to fill research and development gaps identified by the EJP SOIL’s WP2 “Roadmap for EU Agricultural Soil Management research”.

1.3 Scope and expected impacts and outputs of this EJP SOIL call

The present EJP SOIL call will contribute to long-term alignment of research strategies in two main ways: **i)** by developing a shared vision, and **ii)** establishing platforms for networks of soil scientist and other soil stakeholders in Europe. The shared vision will be developed among consortium beneficiaries and will address desirable soil futures and ways to attain them. This process was initiated during the preparation of the proposal and will continue with the preparation of a roadmap for soil research, setting objectives, actions and milestones. Internal calls will foster alignment between the EJP SOIL beneficiaries, linked third parties and important players of European research in the areas of agriculture, ecology, soils and climate. To facilitate relevant knowledge development the EJP SOIL will perform **i) synthesis and stock taking activities and ii) research and integrative projects:**

Stocktaking activities is an inventory. This term is used when an inventory of given information is searched in a systematic way across the EJP SOIL participating countries.

Syntheses are used to gather and synthesise information without systematic country scale inventory.

Research projects will answer a research question or a set of research questions. A research project must include a description of a defined protocol, clearly articulated goal(s), defined methods and outputs, and a defined start and end date.

Approved (by the Board of Project Managers) topics of the stock-taking activities and research projects will be managed through internal calls; for more details see below section 2.

2 Call topics

Interested project consortia should apply to one of EJP SOIL call topics:

Table 1: Targeted EJP SOIL topics of the 1st call projects; their sizes, number and available funding. For detailed description see Appendix 2. Project sizes are explained in detail in section 6.3.

EJP SOIL ID	Title	Number and size (PM)	Indicative available funding
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EJP SOIL topics: **CM** Climate change mitigation; **CA** Climate change adaptation; **FS** Food security; **MT** Multi-topics; **ES** Ecosystem services; **SR** Soil restoration

3. Budget, funding modalities and eligibility criteria

The EJP SOIL is a 5 year project that runs from February 2020 to January 2025. The EJP SOIL falls into the concept of a co-fund action. **For the 1st call of EJP SOIL projects a budget of maximum 15 M€ can be allocated.**

Only EJP SOIL beneficiaries and third linked parties (see Appendix 1) can apply. After the closing date for submission all proposals will be checked against the mandatory Call eligibility criteria:

- Applications must be written in English.
- Applications must be complete and in accordance to the submission procedure.
- Applications must be submitted in time.
- Proposals of applying consortia including beneficiaries and/or third linked parties that are NOT EJP SOIL beneficiaries are not eligible to apply and will be rejected.

EJP SOIL experts who are involved in the internal call preparation (i.e. Nils Borchard, Johanna Leppälä, Rosemarie Stangl, Pia Minixhofer, Elena Rodriguez, Violeta Carrasco) are not eligible to apply for EJP SOIL internal funding. For further questions regarding the eligibility criteria, please contact the Call Office (see above).

4 Project types

Depending on the topic and type of project required, the proposal must meet the following specific call eligibility criteria:

- **Stocktake²**: 2 leaders; duration between 3 to 12 months; 40 PM with in minimum 1 PM per consortium partner, distribution of remaining PMs is flexible.
- **Synthesis**: 1 leader plus additional consortium partners (typically 3); duration between 3 and 12 months; 20 PM.
- **Small sized project**: minimum 3 consortium partners; duration between 6 and 12 months; between 50 and 100 PM.
- **Medium sized project**: minimum 5 consortium partners with geographical coverage requested in the topics of this call; inclusiveness is of high importance; duration between 12 and 36 months; about 150 PM.
- **Large sized project**: minimum 10 consortium partners with geographical coverage requested in the topics of this call; inclusiveness is of high importance; duration between 36 and 48 months; about 350 PM.

The number of associated PMs are indicative. Large projects could associate all beneficiaries of the consortium. Depending on the topics, only one project or several can be eligible.

² Stocktakes are inventories or in other words a systematic way to gather information across the EJP SOIL participating countries. Stocktakes will be coordinated by one beneficiary, possibly with a deputy lead and will. The coordinating beneficiary will send a request for information to all EJP SOIL beneficiaries, e.g. questionnaires. Gathered information will be assessed and published in form of a report. All participants will be requested to provide this information for their country and the lead – co-lead will synthesize and analyse the received information and elaborate a report.

Annex 1. EJP SOIL beneficiaries and their linked third parties

Member states	EJP SOIL beneficiaries and their linked third parties	Contact (Name and e-mail)
	Institut National de recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement – INRAE Linked third parties: AgroParisTech, AgroCampus Ouest, SupAgro Montpellier	Chantal Gascuel chantal.gascuel@inrae.fr
	Stichting Wageningen Research – WR	Saskia Visser saskia.visser@wur.nl
	Verein zur Förderung der Lebenswissenschaften – BIOS Linked third parties: BOKU, AGES, BAW, BFW, Environment Agency Austria	Sophie Zechmeister-Boltenstern sophie.zechmeister@boku.ac.at
	Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food – EV-ILVO Third linked parties: EV INBO, VPO	Greet Ruyschaert Greet.ruyschaert@ilvo.vlaanderen.be
	Centre Wallon de Recherches Agronomiques – CRAW	Bruno Huyghebaert b.huyghebaert@cra.wallonie.be
	Czech University of Life Sciences – CZU	Luboš Borůvka boruvka@af.czu.cz
	Aarhus University, Danish Centre for Food and Agriculture – AU	Lars Munkholm lars.munkholm@agro.au.dk
	Estonian University of Life Sciences – EMU Linked third party: ARC	Alar Astover alar.astover@emu.ee
	Luonnonvarakeskus - Natural Resources Institute Finland – LUKE	Nils Borchard nils.borchard@luke.fi
	Johann Heinrich von Thünen-Institut – Thunen	Axel Don axel.don@thuenen.de
	Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH – Julich	N/A
	Agricultural Research Centre Agrártudományi Kutatóközpont – MTA ATK	Zsófia Bakacsi bakacsi.zsafia@agrar.mta.hu
	Teagasc – The Agriculture and Food Development Authority – Teagasc	David Wall david.wall@teagasc.ie
	Council for Agricultural Research and Economics – CREA Linked third parties: CNR, ISPRA, UNIPA, ENEA, AGRIS, ERSAF Lombardia	Rosario Napoli rosario.napoli@crea.gov.it
	University of Latvia – UL	Raimonds Kasparinskis raimonds.kasparinskis@lu.lv

Member states	EJP SOIL beneficiaries and their linked third parties	Contact (Name and e-mail)
	Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry – LAMMC	Zydre Kadziuliene zydre.kadziuliene@lammc.lt
	Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research – NIBIO	Daniel Rasse daniel.rasse@nibio.no
	Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation – State Research Institute – IUNG	Bożena Smerczak bozenas@iung.pulawy.pl
	National Institute for Agrarian and Veterinarian Research I. P. – INIAV	Maria da Conceição Gonçalves maria.goncalves@iniav.pt
	National Agricultural and Food Centre – NPPC	Dana Peškovičová dana.peskovicova@npppc.sk
	University of Ljubljana – UL Linked third party: AIS, UM-FKBV	Helena Grčman Helena.Grcman@bf.uni-lj.si
	National Institute for Agriculture and Food Research and Technology - INIA	Elena Rodríguez-Valín rodriguez.elena@inia.es
	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences – SLU	Anke Herrmann anke.herrmann@slu.se
	Agroscope – AGS	Gina Garland gina.garland@agroscope.admin.ch
	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies – TAGEM	Sevinç Madenoglu sevinc.madenoglu@tarimorman.gov.tr
	Agri-Food and Biosciences Institute – AFBI	Dario Fornara Dario.fornara@afbini.gov.uk

Annex 2. EJP SOIL call topics (preliminary description)

Title:

Rationale:

Scope:

Output/Expected impact:

Project type:

Relation to EJP SOIL objectives and tasks:

SOP-OC 01 Annex 1b (Final call-announcement)

Please see 1st and 2nd EJP SOIL Call text prepared, launched in June 2020 (M05) and May 2021 (M16); see also D3.2 “Call text of the EJP SOIL 1st internal call” and D3.4 “Call text of the EJP SOIL 2nd internal call”.

SOP-OC 01 Annex 2 (Letter of commitment)

To be submitted after selection.

This template may be used for participants of selected research projects in order to provide evidence of their commitment. Grey-marked fields must be duly completed. This document must be signed by an authorized representative of the organisation. A template for each participant organization is required.

In case of failure in proving such commitment, the participants could be regarded as ineligible, jeopardizing the whole research consortium.

EJP SOIL Call Office	Address of organisation
Organisation	Name of contact person
Name	
Street	
Town	
Country	

EJP SOIL – 1st Internal Call for research proposals 2020
Letter of commitment
Project title: ...

Place, date

We hereby confirm that **organisation** has sufficient resources and is committed to participate to the **project title**, in accordance to the proposal which is submitted by coordinator in the frame of the EJP SOIL – 1st Internal Call 2020 and in case the proposal is selected for funding by the joint Call Group.

In addition, in case of separate source of funding: Please find attached to this letter a commitment from **funding organisation** for our contribution to this project.

Signature of **Name and affiliation**

SOP-OC 01 Annex 3 (Reporting template)

1. Background

The coordinator of each funded project is required to submit regularly monitoring reports (three times a year), to be integrated within the EJP SOIL summary progress and annual technical reports, and a final report for each project despite of their size summarizing the work achieved within the project consortium as well as some impact related questions. The project partners are asked to support the coordinator and should themselves enter and/ or update specific parts within the report regarding partner details and some impact related questions.

The reporting shall be performed by using the provided word template(s) found in project-specific folders in the data secure EJP SOIL SharePoint.

The reporting template is currently under revision as monitoring approaches of WP1, WP5, WP8 and WP9 will be integrated into the WP3 continuous reporting approach.

2. Basic project information

Project title:	XXX
Acronym:	XXX
Duration:	Dates
Topic:	XXX
Project type:	e.g. Large-sized/small-sized project
Project coordinator:	XXX, Institute
Abstract:	150-250 words giving a short overview of the project aims, methods (and key results/achievements, if available)
Key words:	Words or phrases that describe the content of the project
Key Takeaways:	1-5 simple statements that distil the main takeaway messages from the project goals targeted to a general audience
Project partners:	Participation and coordination highlighted in grey.

Beneficiary no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Abbreviation	INRAE	WR	BIOS/BO KU	EV-ILVO	CRAW	CZU	AU	EMU	LUKE	Thuenen	Juelich	MTA-ATK	Teagasc
Person-months	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-
Beneficiary no.	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
Abbreviation	CREA	UL	LAMMAC	NIBIO	IJUNG	INIAV	NPPC	ULBF	INIA-CSIC	SLU	AGS	TAGAM	AFBI
Person-months	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-
LTP no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13

Abbreviation	AgroParisTec	Institut Agro	EAA	AGES	BAW	BFW	EV INBO	VPO	ARC	CNR	ISPRA	UNIPA	ENEA
Person-months	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-
LTPno.	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
Abbreviation	AGRIS	ERSAF	AIS +	UM-FKBV	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-
Person-months	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-	-/-

3. Monitoring periods and instructions for reporting

Please see below the monitoring periods and deadlines for the monitoring reports.

Instructions: Sections 3.1 – 3.3 of the report need to be updated 3 times a year (May, September, February), and the sections 3.4 – 3.9 only once a year in connection with annual technical report (February) and at the end of the respective project. Note that you need to anticipate the activities of the two last weeks of each period, except the annual reporting in February. The report has to be uploaded in the [EJP SOIL SharePoint](#). Please create and save a new version of the document in connection with each monitoring period. The file name should indicate the date of the report and the number of monitoring period.

Monitoring period (MP) no	Monitoring period dates	Deadline for the monitoring report -> need to be uploaded in the EJP SOIL SharePoint	Sections of the report to be updated
MP1	01.02.2021 – 31.03.2021	15.03.2021	Sections 3.1 -3.3
MP2	01.04.2021 – 30.05.2021	15.05.2021	Sections 3.1 -3.3
MP3	01.06.2021 – 31.09.2021	15.09.2021	Sections 3.1 -3.3
MP4	01.10.2021 – 31.01.2022	15.02.2022	All sections
MP5	01.02.2022 – 31.05.2022	15.05.2022	Sections 3.1 -3.3
MP6	01.06.2022 – 31.09.2022	15.09.2022	Sections 3.1 -3.3
MP7	01.10.2022 – 31.01.2023	15.02.2023	All sections
MP8	01.02.2023 – 30.05.2023	15.05.2023	Sections 3.1 -3.3
MP9	01.06.2023 – 31.09.2023	15.09.2023	Sections 3.1 -3.3
MP10	01.10.2023 – 31.01.2024	15.02.2024	All sections
MP11	01.02.2024 – 30.05.2024	15.05.2024	Sections 3.1 -3.3
MP12	01.06.2024 – 31.09.2024	15.09.2024	Sections 3.1 -3.3
MP13	01.10.2024 – 31.01.2025	15.02.2025	All sections, final report

3.1 Continuous reporting

- Summary of the work carried out
- Work carried out by each WP, including project meetings
- Key progress since the previous report
- Details on milestones achieved and deliverables submitted
- *Please also clearly indicate changes and modifications (deviations, delays etc.) as compared to the original work plan, as well as corrective measures taken to e.g. avoid further delays.*
- *min 2 pages*

The sections 3.4 – 3.10 need to be completed only once a year as part of the annual technical report.

3.4 Summary of the scientific information and results

Project Objectives: Short statements on the aims to be completed by the project.

Please summarize the main scientific exploitable results achieved from the project start (1st February) to 31st of January and how they have contributed to reaching the 6 EJP SOIL Expected Impacts. Max 1000 words, 2 pages.

3.5 Teaching and education activities

Please fill /record for the monitoring of capacity building and involvement of early career scientist in EJP SOIL supported activities

Category	Home institution	Number of persons involved	Is the candidate(s) listed contributor or main author on project outputs (refer to section 3.10) (YES/NO)
MSc- level student, including thesis			
PhD level			
Post doc level			

3.6 Unexpected results and opportunities

What was the **most surprising research result with this project** in terms of research findings: Did you achieve unexpected or unintended results? *(Please describe both positive or less positive surprise elements)*

Did this project find new and/or unexpected opportunities to share project results and findings: Did you achieve unexpected or unintended engagement and outreach opportunities, not originally in the project plan? *(Please describe emerging opportunities/unplanned achievements that were realized by this project, especially related to outreach/communication/engagement to share results with academic or non-academic audiences and partners.)*

Will the activities under this project **continue in some form**? How/What will be taken forward?

3.7 Summary of critical risks

Please explain evolved and anticipated risks affecting implementation of project tasks and activities, their severity and mitigation measures proposed or implemented.

Evolved and anticipated risks	Severity (low, medium, high)	Planned or implemented mitigation measure

3.8 List of publications and other outputs

Please note that dissemination and communication activities are reported separately (by WP9 of the EJP SOIL, Line Carlenius Berggreen). Thus, please keep it short here and list the following:

- publications produced by the project: peer reviewed publications and their DOI numbers, articles in journals, publications in conference proceedings or workshops, books or monographs, book chapters, theses/dissertations,
- other outputs of the project, *and links to them if possible*, e.g. patents, trainings, software, databases etc.
- presentations and outreach workshops, seminars etc.

3.9 Information Capture for WP8

Relevance to EJP SOIL

Please check all boxes that apply to your project.

Relevant policy domains

- Climate change mitigation
- Climate change adaptation
- Ecosystem services
- Food security
- Avoiding land degradation

Relevant research areas

- Sustainable agricultural production
- C sequestration
- Healthy soils
- Land and soil restoration
- Soil biodiversity
- Ecosystem services

Relevant impact areas

- Climate mitigation
- Climate adaptation
- Sustainable production
- Sustainable environment
- Networking & knowledge sharing
- Harmonising
- Adoption of sustainable management
- Science to policy interface

Relevant projects

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> CarboSeq | <input type="checkbox"/> SensRes |
| <input type="checkbox"/> SOMMIT | <input type="checkbox"/> SCALE |
| <input type="checkbox"/> TRACE- Soils | <input type="checkbox"/> i-SoMPE |
| <input type="checkbox"/> INSURE | <input type="checkbox"/> SIREN |
| <input type="checkbox"/> STEROPES | <input type="checkbox"/> CLIMASOMA |

Relevant soil challenges

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Maintain/ increase SOC | <input type="checkbox"/> Avoid contamination |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Avoid N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions | <input type="checkbox"/> Optimal soil structure |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Avoid peat degradation | <input type="checkbox"/> Enhance soil biodiversity |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Avoid soil erosion | <input type="checkbox"/> Enhance soil nutrient retention/ use efficiency |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Avoid soil sealing | <input type="checkbox"/> Enhance water storage capacity |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Avoid salinization | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Avoid acidification | |

Relevant knowledge framework

- Knowledge development
- Knowledge sharing and transfer
- Knowledge harmonisation, organisation and storage
- Knowledge application

Areas/ topics requiring further research

Relevance to Policymakers

Relevant / targeted stakeholders

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Researchers | <input type="checkbox"/> Interest groups |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Education | <input type="checkbox"/> Advisory |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Local policymakers | <input type="checkbox"/> Extension |
| <input type="checkbox"/> National policymakers | <input type="checkbox"/> Farmers |
| <input type="checkbox"/> EU policymakers | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input type="checkbox"/> International policymakers | |

Aspects of policy that can be informed

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Data/Evidence for policy | <input type="checkbox"/> management) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring | <input type="checkbox"/> Laws |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Reporting (e.g. Input of GHG emissions into IPCC) | <input type="checkbox"/> Recommendations |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Verification | <input type="checkbox"/> Tools (e.g. soil navigator, LANDMARK2020) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Practices (e.g. EIP best practices for soil | |

Relevant policy areas

E.g. agricultural production, environmental protection, evaluating ecosystem services etc.

Instruments that can be informed

- Market
- Mandatory
- Voluntary
- Incentives
- AKIS
- Regulatory
- Information

Suggested policy recommendations & their target audience

E.g. Indicator X developed in this project presents an opportunity to accurately measure C sequestered in the soil – National / Regional Policymakers

E.g. The creation of this decision support tool that can be used to help farmers implement best practices – Extension officers/ Education

SOP-OE 01 Annex 1 (Letter of request)

*European Commission
Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
Director-General
ORBN 03/136
B-1049 Brussels*

Subject: Request for access to the European Commission database of experts

Dear Sir and Madam!

We kindly request to getting granted access to EC database of experts to ensure appropriate evaluation of proposals prepared by EJP Soil partners aiming to apply for EJP internal funding (project no.: 862 695; coordinated by Prof. Dr Claire Chenu). The experts should at least cover following disciplines: Soil Science, Organic Soils, Agriculture, and Agro-Ecology.

Granted access will be limited to two individuals who are the leader of WP3 “Internal Calls” (Nils Borchard) and his deputy (Bartosz Adamczyk).

Contact details of person who ask for access:

Dr Nils Borchard (Nils.Borchard@luke.fi)

Dr Bartosz Adamczyk (Bartosz.Adamczyk@luke.fi)

Kind regards,
Nils Borchard
Bartosz Adamczyk

SOP-OE 01 Annex 2 (Non-disclosure agreement & Declaration of Conflict of Interest)

EJP SOIL – Internal Calls for proposals 2020 CONFIDENTIALITY NON-DISCLOSURE AGREEMENT

DATE: DD MMM YYYY

I hereby undertake to treat as confidential all and any information that I receive while participating in the work of the EJP SOIL's joint call Expert Pool (EP) and evaluating project proposals, to use this information solely for the purpose of evaluation of the proposals, not to disclose it to any third party and not to make it publicly available or accessible in any way, except with the prior written consent of the joint call consortium.

I understand that this confidentiality non-disclosure agreement is binding towards the joint call network, who has appointed me as an evaluator and towards (and for the benefit of) any applicant submitting the project proposal to the 1st EJP SOIL call for proposals. Furthermore, I understand that this confidentiality non-disclosure agreement concerns all and any information in any form that comes to my knowledge during my participation in the work of the joint call Expert Panel and evaluating respective project proposals.

I understand that I shall be bound by this confidentiality non-disclosure agreement as on the date of receipt of this signed letter by the Call Office, and that this confidentiality should be maintained even after the Expert Panel has performed its duties or after my participation in the work of the Expert Panel has ended.

I will not identify myself as a reviewer to the applicant(s) or to any third party, while the Call Office will ensure confidentiality concerning my role as reviewer as well. I will only address any questions concerning a proposal to the Call Office and not to the applicant(s).

Declaration of conflict of interest

I declare that I will independent, impartial and objective in the evaluation of the assigned proposals. I will refrain from reviewing the proposal if a conflict of interest exists or could be perceived to exist. I understand that there is a conflict of interest if I stand to profit professionally, financially or personally from approval or rejection of the proposal; if in the past three years I have published with, cooperated with or worked at the same company or research unit as the applicant or any of the project workers; if I have fundamental differences of scientific opinion with any applicant; or if I'm a friend or relative of the applicant or any of the co-workers.

If any such conflict of interest exists or arises, I will inform the Call Office as soon as possible. The Call Office takes the last decision about conflicts of interest and disqualifications. I will follow the indications given by the Call Office aiming at reaching an impartial evaluation of the proposals

CODE OF CONDUCT AGREEMENT

Fundamental principles of good research practice and peer-review are essential for research integrity. All parties involved directly or indirectly in the evaluation must ensure the transparency and fairness of the process, the evaluation criteria published are respected equally for all proposals, and public funds are well used:

1. Experts as members of the EP are chosen for their technical or scientific or industrial expertise to cover the topics addressed by the submitted proposals. They should perform their work to the best of their abilities, professional skills, knowledge and applying the highest ethical and moral standards.
2. All parties involved directly or indirectly in the evaluation must act objectively, with no self-interested motives. They do not represent their company, organisation or establishment.
3. The reviewers shall evaluate the proposals based solely upon the information contained in the proposals and in accordance with the Evaluation Guidelines.
4. The experts must immediately inform the Call Office if they cannot fulfil their obligations.
5. The reviewers shall finish the individual written assessment for proposals by DD MMM YYYY at the latest; shall be available for discussions with other evaluators for the consolidation of the consensus report and agree to provide contact details to other evaluators.
6. EP members should refrain in all cases from identifying external experts to third parties, and from divulging any other information which could compromise their anonymity. Likewise, reviewers cannot contact the applicants nor the other reviewers during the individual evaluation of proposals.
7. If any reviewer is subject to any pressure whatsoever from a project partner, she or he must immediately notify the Call Office.
8. If there is a **conflict of interest**, the concerned person must inform the Call Office as soon as finding that a conflict exists. The necessary measures will be taken to ensure that the related decision will not be biased, or suspected to be so.
9. Compensations will be paid only if tasks were accomplished in accordance with the provisions of the Evaluation guidelines, within the given deadlines and in high quality after approval by the Board of Programme Managers. Compensations may not be paid in case of breach of obligations relating to this Code of Conduct.

I agree to the rules of the confidentiality NON-disclosure agreement,

I undertake to abide by the Code of Conduct for Reviewers of the EJP-Soil Internal Call:

NO

YES

SOP-OE 01 Annex 3 (Evaluation guidelines)

Definitions

Board of Programme managers

The Board of Programme Managers (BPM) is the ultimate decision-making body of the project. It is composed of one representative programme manager per country. Chaired by the BPM Chair, the BPM will take decisions (1 vote per country) based on a majority vote. In countries with more than one programme manager, consensus should be sought between the participating organisations to contribute one single vote to the EJP SOIL decisions.

Call Office:

Central contact point for all issues around the evaluation procedures of the call (as well as the application procedure).

Expert pool (EP):

Group of experts who will peer-review the submitted proposals in the framework of the Internal Call. The EP will be composed of international experts based on their acknowledged expertise in the research areas covered by the submitted proposals.

Background of the Call

About the EJP SOIL

The EJP SOIL will maximize the contribution of agricultural soil towards achieving sustainability at multiple levels: **i) At the societal level:** raise public awareness and foster understanding of sustainable agricultural soil management and its contribution to food production, climate change adaptation and mitigation; **ii) At the scientific level:** develop new insights on climate-smart soil management, quantify trade-offs and synergies between agricultural production, climate change adaptation and mitigation, soil fertility and health and other ecosystem services; gather new knowledge on carbon sequestration in soils under different conditions across Europe and its contribution to climate change mitigation; improve accounting and reporting tools for emission and removals from agricultural activities; **iii) At the operational level:** strengthen the European research community on agricultural soil management; develop harmonized soil information systems and promote their adoption; **iv) At the policy level:** develop evidence-based recommendations for policy makers at EU, national, and regional levels; establish a strategic multi-actor approach and initiate a science-policy-practitioner-society dialogue on agricultural soil health and adequate agricultural practices to support the adoption of the policy recommendations; foster the uptake of climate-smart sustainable soil management practices by practitioners.

Rationale of this call

As EJP SOIL works on important societal issues in an integrated manner, any innovation developed within the framework of EJP SOIL will meet a societal need and will therefore be relevant for European and global markets. Through its knowledge framework, EJP SOIL improves its innovation capacity using 1) **knowledge development**, 2) knowledge sharing & transfer, 3) knowledge organization & storage for 4) knowledge application in different areas. **Knowledge development** will be supported by the EJP SOIL through a large number of specific research and innovation projects via internal (i.e. WP3 “Internal Calls”) and external EJP SOIL calls. The overall objective of this internal call launched in MXX (see D3.2 “Call text of the EJP SOIL 1st internal call”) is to fund stocktaking activities, syntheses, and research projects open to EJP SOIL partners and linked third parties (LTP) according to the consortium agreement to fill research and development gaps identified by the EJP SOIL’s WP2 “Roadmap for EU Agricultural Soil Management research”.

Topic-specific scope, expected impacts and outputs of this EJP SOIL call

Placeholder for topic-specific call text; see Annex 1 of D3.2 “Call text of the EJP SOIL 1st internal call”.

Time schedule

The envisaged time schedule for the evaluation process of the Internal Call is indicated in the table below:

Table 2: Time schedule for evaluation of proposals.

Action	Schedule
Submission of proposals	DD MMM – DD MMM YYYY
Nomination of experts for the EP	DD MMM – DD MMM YYYY
Assignment of proposals to experts and submission of Confidentiality non-disclosure agreement/ Code of conduct agreement as well as COI	DD MMM – DD MMM YYYY 2 weeks time period after nomination
Evaluation of proposals	DD MMM YYYY – DD MMM YYYY (usually we give them 1.5 up to 2 month, depending on amount of proposals they have to evaluate)
Preparation of evaluation summaries by rapporteur	Until DD MMM YYYY
Selection of proposals by BPM	DD MMM YYYY

Call Office

The Call Office will provide administrative support to the experts during the evaluation process. It is the primary point of contact between the International Expert Panel (IEP) members and the BPM for all general matters in relation to the peer-review evaluation.

Contact persons:

NAME:	Nils Borchard	Johanna Leppälä
Organisation:	LUKE	LUKE
Phone:	+358 29 5322 201	+358 29 5322 559

E-mail:	EJPCO@maapera.fi	EJPCO@maapera.fi
NAME:	Rosemarie Stangl	Pia Minixhofer
Organisation:	BIOS/BOKU	BIOS/BOKU
Phone:	+43 1 47854 87401	+43 1 47854 87406
E-mail:	EJPCO@maapera.fi	EJPCO@maapera.fi

The evaluation procedure after submission of the research proposals

The assessment of the submitted proposals (eligibility checks, evaluation by the EP members) will be carried out using step wise: i) the WP3 of the EJP SOIL will check for eligibility criteria of this call prior ii) forwarding eligible proposals to selected and invited evaluators who will review in accordance to rules described in this guideline.

Expert Pool (EP)

The Expert Pool (EP) for evaluation is constituted of internationally recognised Experts chosen for their scientific / technical expertise and knowledge of the sectors covered in the Call. The European Commission database of experts has also been consulted. Potential experts have been invited to become members of the EP and have sent their application to the Call Office. The selection of International Expert Pool members is made by the Call Office. Experts are contacted by the Call Office for confirmation of availability and the assignment of proposals. An expert can only become a member of the EP if s/he has no conflict of interest and is available during the evaluation process. The final number of experts to build the IEP depends on the number of proposals submitted, the topics addressed and the expertise of the evaluators. Experts are asked to contact the Call Office in case they do not feel their area of expertise matches the assigned proposals. The names of EP members will be kept anonymous for the applicants through the whole procedure.

Performing the Evaluation

Conflict of Interest, confidentiality and code of conduct

Before performing an evaluation, the confidentiality NON-disclosure agreement and Code of Conduct ([SOP-OE 01 Annex 2](#)) need to be printed, signed and sent back to the Call office. For each proposal, the assigned expert will then need to decide on possible Conflict of Interest ([SOP-OE 01 Annex 2](#)), based on a summary and research consortium information of the proposal. Full access to a proposal will only be granted when no conflict of interest exists.

Task of the EP

The EP shall peer review proposals and provide consolidated evaluation feedback within the given timeframes (see Table 1 of this document). Thereby, each proposal is evaluated by three experts. In case of highly contradictory evaluations an additional expert or the EP chair could be invited to a further evaluation. The evaluation summary shall be a consolidated by the Call Office based on the EP's scoring. The proposal and evaluation summary will be forwarded to the BPM for approval.

Evaluation criteria

All eligible proposals will be evaluated by 3 experts according to the following three criteria:

1. **Excellence:** Coherence and pertinence of the objectives, contribution to the scope of the 1st EJP SOIL Call and the selected topic Scientific quality of objectives, ambition in relation to the call scope and topic addressed and innovative progress beyond the state-of-the-art.,
2. **Implementation:** Appropriateness and soundness of the research approach and methodology, feasibility, effectiveness of the work plan, complementarity/competences/ diversity of partners and disciplines, adequacy of the budget and balance between partners in terms of activities, risk management, capacity building activities, communication and dissemination.
3. **Impact:** Potential to reach expected impact and innovate/ implement, embracing of cross-cutting issues , added value of transnational cooperation, geographical coverage, contribution towards sustainable soil management, innovation potential, transnational added value, etc.

Evaluation scores

For each evaluation criterion, scores from 0 to 5 (half points allowed) are awarded. A threshold of 3/5 will be applied for each criterion, i.e. proposals with a mean score < 3 in any criterion will not be recommended for funding. The overall score will be the sum of the mean scores of the 3 evaluation criteria and will include one decimal behind the comma (min 0.0, max 15.0). The following scoring scheme should be applied:

Table 3: Score scheme for evaluation of the proposals.

0	Weak	The proposal shows severe flaws that are intrinsic to the proposed project. The criterion under examination is not addressed or cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information.
1	Poor	The proposal addresses the criterion unsatisfactorily or in an inadequate manner. It shows serious inherent weaknesses resulting in the need of substantial modification or improvement.
2	Fair	The proposal broadly addresses the criterion; however, it contains some weaknesses and elements that can be improved.
3	Good	The proposal addresses the criterion well; however, it contains few elements that could be improved.
4	Very Good	The proposal is really good in international comparison and contains no significant elements to be improved. It addresses the criterion very well, although certain improvements are still possible.
5	Excellent	The proposal stands out with exceptional novelty, innovation and progress of science at global level. It successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion in question. Any shortcomings are minor

Besides the scores, the written statements (evaluation reports) should reflect the score, be sufficiently detailed and comprehensible.

Ethics assessment

Experts' evaluation will include the check of Ethical issues using the information provided by the applicants, as explained at section 5 "Ethics assessment" of the Call Announcement. The assessment has to refer to the criteria published by the Commission in its guidelines for the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme, also listed in the self-assessment applicants are invited to perform (see http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/ethics/h2020_hi_ethics-self-assess_en.pdf). Any proposal, which seems to contravene fundamental ethical principles, may be excluded from selection.

Evaluation reports

All experts will provide a written evaluation report (see SOP-OE 01 Annex 5) on strengths and weaknesses of each proposal. The report has to be sufficiently detailed and in line with the given score. In case of a proposal failing to reach the threshold, a clear and consistent justification should be given. Evaluators will write an evaluation report (ca. half a page) for the proposals assigned. In case of strongly contradictory reviews among the 3 evaluators, the Call Office should involve an additional expert.

Compensation

The EJP SOIL offers a remuneration of 100 EUR per evaluated proposal.

SOP-OE 01 Annex 4 (Single proposal evaluation report)

Evaluation report template (see also SOP-OC 01 Annex 1b)

<p>Excellence Note:</p> <p>The following aspects will be taken into account, to the extent that the proposed work corresponds to the topic description in the call text under the relevant topic:</p> <p>Relevant for large, medium and small sized research projects (see section 2 and Annex 2):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity, pertinence and scientific quality of objectives, ambition in relation to the call scope and topic addressed and innovative progress beyond the state-of-the-art; • Appropriate consideration of interdisciplinary approaches and, where relevant, use of stakeholder knowledge in research and innovation content; • Soundness of the concept, and credibility of the proposed methodology; <p>Relevant for large sized projects (see section 2 and Annex 2):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of ambition in the collaboration and commitment of the participants in the proposed large sized projects to pool national resources in terms number of consortium beneficiaries and/or linked third parties and participating countries. <p>Relevant for stocktaking activities and syntheses (see section 2 of this document and Annex 2):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity and pertinence of the objectives; • Soundness of the concept, and credibility of the proposed methodology. <p><u>Comments:</u></p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Score</p>
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<p>Impact Note:</p> <p>The following aspects will be taken into account to the extent to which the outputs of the project would contribute to each of the expected impacts mentioned in the call text under the relevant topic:</p> <p>Relevant for all project types listed in table 1 (see section 2 of this document and Annex 2):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The extent to which the outputs of the project would contribute to each of the expected impacts mentioned in the topic-specific call text, see Annex 2; <p>Relevant for large, medium and small sized research projects (see section 2 of this document and Annex 2):</p>	
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any substantial impacts not mentioned in the topic-specific call text (Annex 2), that would enhance innovation capacity, address issues related to sustainable and climate smart soil management, or bring other important benefits for society • Contribution to establishing and strengthening a durable cooperation between the consortium beneficiaries and/or linked third parties. 	Score
<u>Comments:</u>	

<p>Quality and efficiency of the implementation Note:</p> <p>The following aspects will be taken into account:</p> <p>Relevant for all project types listed in table 1 (see section 2 of this document and Annex 2):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complementarity of the participants and extent to which the consortium as whole brings together the necessary expertise; • Appropriateness of the allocation of tasks, ensuring that all participants have a valid role and adequate resources in the project to fulfil that role. <p>Relevant for large, medium and small sized research projects (see section 2 of this document and Annex 2):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality and effectiveness of the work plan, including extent to which the resources assigned to work packages are in line with their objectives and deliverables; • Appropriateness of the management structures and procedures, including risk and innovation management. 	Score
<u>Comments:</u>	

Total score (1+2+3)

SOP-OE 01 Annex 5 (Call evaluation report)

Evaluation report template

ID	Acronym	Total score	Threshold	Relevance	Implementation	Excellence	Impact	Final recommendation
			passed					accept
			failed					reject

Text explaining in more detail evaluation results per criteria:

Relevance:

Implementation:

Excellence:

Impact:

SOP-OM 01 Annex 1 (Key performance indicators)

List of potential performance indicators applied in WP3

Type of indicator	Subtype Indicator	Indicator	key question	Our targets	Source	comment	Question/Template/... for project managers	Fakten/Daten/Aussagen bekommen wir aus	belongs to
Inputs	Effective Management	Coverage of the Internal Call within consortium	No. of submitted proposals	- all partners are involved in at least one project	Call office			general data available at call office	Impact assessment
Inputs	Effective Management	Success rate Internal Call	No. of selected projects	- at least 80% of all proposals are recommended for funding	Call office			general data available at call office	Impact assessment
Inputs	Effective Management	Call process	- Quality of the Call documents - Quality of Website	- more than 90 % voted Call process with grade 2 and better - more than 75 % voted the Call process with grade 3 and better	questionnaire	- survey among all applicants	Possible questions (4 – very good, 3 – good, 2 – fair, 1 – adequate, 0 – insufficient) 1) The Call documents have been understandable and well written 2) The provided Call documents have been sufficient to submit a full proposal without questioning. 3) The matching tool helped to find project partners 4) The call process was transparent and information have been provided in time	Survey	Impact assessment
Inputs	Equipment	Investment	- Rate budget for human resources (Employees, training,) vs. other direct costs (pilot plants,)	get an overview of what is needed to achieve our objectives (human resources vs. other resources)	Call office	- get data from application vs. actual costs - part of the Impact model.... - KPI shall show if investment for equipment/other resources or investment in man power is more needed research in this area	budget table from each funded project	general data available at call office	Impact assessment

Inputs	Expertise	Collaboration with networks/platforms taking into account a multi-actor and system approach	new collaborations formed due to the funded project or have you been able to enhance / enlarge your "contact portfolio", i.e. have you been able to meet different actors along the food chain and engaged in scientific exchange with different actors	enhance interdisciplinary exchange among	survey MTR/ETR	- Important for WP 2 and WP9? --> organizing of networking events/workshops,	- Have you have or will have any collaborations (joint paper, further planned projects,) with other networks/platforms --> describe - How did you find/engage your collaborators? a) existing collaboration b) Conference c) ICT-AGRI platform d) Events organised by any ERA-NET/FACCE	Survey	Impact assessment
Inputs	Funding	Size of projects	- Total grant requested per project - size of consortia (number of partners per project)	none, depends on many factors (e.g. wage level in different countries, Topic, ...)	Call office	important for WP1 (e.g. limits for funding)	budget table from each funded project	general data available at call office	Impact assessment
Inputs	Human Resources	FTEs per consortium Type of employees	Amount of FTE per partner per project and type of (PhD, students, Post Docs, ...)	- funding mode suitable to get experienced research staff - can young researchers be fostered	survey		Question to coordinator and partner of each funded project: - How many FTEs paid with funding and for how long? - type of employee?	Survey	Impact assessment
Inputs	Innovation	Innovative content	Novelty of the project, continuation of existing line of research	- get input for WPs 1, 2, 8 and 9	survey MTR/ETR		Question to coordinator and partner of each funded project: - Was your project completely new or are there any existing results? - if FU project? Type of former funding?	Monitoring	Monitoring

Outputs	Final	Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Established new or improved standards - dissemination of results - developed new improved products? - added value (sustainability resilience) - created new services? - Developed /improved processes? 	get an impression of each individual project how they see the achievements within their project	MTR/ETR		free text with summary on main achievement in this context (not repeating results already mentioned e.g. no. of publications,)	Monitoring	Monitoring
Outputs	Final	Effects on whole agricultural soils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - effects of results towards all actors - risks and benefits for all actors - dissemination of results along the agricultural soil community 	get an overview on how to put the projects into the context of the whole agricultural soil community	MTR/ETR	- also important for impact assessment	tick boxes with actors (Farmer, scientist, others, ...) comment field where risks and benefits are listed	Monitoring	Monitoring
Outputs	Immediate	publications per project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - peer reviewed journals (impact of journals?) - presentations and poster at conferences - seminars - doctoral thesis - interviews - others; 	get an immediate measurable result on dissemination of the results and success of projects	MTR/ETR		provide excel-table for the coordinator of each funded project;	Monitoring	Monitoring
Outputs	Immediate	New partnerships/projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - new partners identified - planned FU activities? - planned FU project? - planned new project? - joint activities 	focus lies on immediate output (max. 1 year after end of project)	MTR/ETR		simple yes/no-questions with possibility to comment of yes is ticked	Monitoring	Monitoring

			with other funding instruments like ERA-NET?						
Outputs	Immediate	Success of project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - all WP and tasks fulfilled? (if not, why?) - all grants have been used? (if not, why?) - Total grant paid vs. Total requested grant - Start and End of project in time (if not, please indicate reason), start within 6 month after recommendation for funding - Entire duration of project - Entire duration for each partner 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - >= 90% of projects shall be successfully closed - >= 80% of the target grants shall be used - >= 90 % of the envisaged tasks/WPs shall be realized - less than 10 % deviation regarding project duration/start 	MTR/ETR		short comment on each WP/Tasks, funded projects shall give reasons if they fail timeline or did not reach expected results	Monitoring	Monitoring
Outputs	Intermediate	New techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - new methods/techniques established? - rank with existing techniques/methods? 	-	MTR/ETR	- also important for impact assessment	provide some tick boxes in context of topic (e.g, new technique in farming) provide score from 1 to 6 for ranking with existing methods: 1 - slightly improvement 2 - improvement 3 - significant improvement 4 - strong improvement (e.g. high impact on reduced resources) 5 - new technique with basics/ideas from existing one 6 - completely new technique/improvement	Monitoring	Monitoring
Outputs	Intermediate	prototypes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - further planning to develop prototype 	-	MTR/ETR	- also important for impact assessment	comment field for future planning	Monitoring	Monitoring

Outputs	Intermediate	patents	/pilots? - submission of patents	-	MTR/ETR	- also important for impact assessment	Tick box --> yes/No --> if yes, write number and tick topic	Monitoring	Monitoring
Outcomes	Economy & strategy	Exploitation of results	- FU planned? (Spin-off, FU projects,) - Dissemination - strengthen competitiveness - new jobs created? (Spin-off, add. funding, ...)	focus lies on outcomes which are in near future (more than 5 years after end of project)	ETR		Tick boxes with the questions and comment field, if "Yes" is ticked	Monitoring	Monitoring
Outcomes	Economy & strategy	Stakeholder Engagement	- stakeholders are partners in consortium? - contact with Stakeholders? - collaboration with stakeholders?	- >= 80 % of the projects have collaborations with stakeholders in either way	MTR/ETR			Monitoring	Monitoring
Outcomes	Economy & strategy	Translational advantage	- added value to put the project translationally? - any results which have been depended on the whole consortium?	why was it necessary to have an European project instead of a national one?	MTR/ETR			Monitoring	Monitoring
Outcomes	Immediate	Management of project	- Deviations in WPs/Tasks? (reasons) - progress --> WPs/Tasks fulfilled in time? (reasons) - objectives achieved? (reasons) - entire success of project/management/cooperation?	- less than 20 % deviation in time plan and WPs/tasks	MTR/ETR			Monitoring	Monitoring

			- consortium as a whole successful?					
Outcomes	Knowledge	leverage on research	- Increased research activity (e.g. junior research group; new employee, ...) - new equipment	focus lies on outcomes which are in near future (more than 5 years after end of project)	MTR/ETR	Type of increased research activities as tick boxes free text field for new equipment	Monitoring	Monitoring
Outcomes	Network & cooperation	Leverage on Networking & cooperation	- New partnerships? - collaboration between different fields in Agri-Food-chain - Integration with existing research and innovations strategies - contacts with stakeholders?	focus lies on outcomes which are in near future (more than 5 years after end of project)	MTR/ETR		Monitoring	Monitoring
Outcomes	Network & cooperation	shared equipment/infrastructure/platforms/data bases	- Shared equipment/infrastructure/platforms/Data bases - Difficulties?		MTR/ETR		Monitoring	Monitoring
Outcomes	Network & cooperation	Success of Cofunded Call	- summary				Monitoring	Monitoring
Impacts	Commercialisation of results	Innovation	- Future planning - classify results in context of research to new product	put results in wider context	MTR/ETR			
Impacts	Implementation of results	Implementation	- How does the results influence your future work? - dissemination with relevant stakeholders?	put results in wider context	MTR/ETR			

Impacts	New data standards	Innovation	- Does your project implement new data standards?	put results in wider context	MTR/ETR
Impacts	Research community	Dissimination	- Impact of results in connection with existing state of the art?	put results in wider context	MTR/ETR
Long-term impacts	Coordination of European policy	Strategy	- Influence on further European policy - contacts with relevant stakeholders? - Influence of each project and whole Cofounded Call (summary on publications and dissemination of results, ...)	put results in wider context	MTR/ETR
Long-term impacts	Food and Quality Transperency		- Contribution of your results in objective of more transparent food system (e.g. transparence in farming,)	put results in wider context	MTR/ETR
Long-term impacts	Implement ICT in agriculture	only topic 1	- Summary of all projects dealing with Topic 1 - Summary of all fundamental achievements (patents, new products, Spin-offs,)	put results in wider context	MTR/ETR
Long-term impacts	Reduced environmental impact		- Summary of all projects in context with reduced	put results in wider context	MTR/ETR

		environmental impact		
Long-term impacts	Sustainability and resilience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have you met your objectives within context of sustainability and resilience (e.g. decrease of fertilizer,) - summary of projects in context of sustainability and resilience, highlight achievements 	put results in wider context	MTR/ETR